

THE SMARANDACHE FUNCTION

E. Radescu , N. Radescu , C. Dumitrescu

It is said that for every numerical function f it can be attached the sumatory function :

$$F(n) = \sum_{d|n} f(d) \quad (1)$$

The function f is expressed as :

$$f(n) = \sum_{uv=n} \mu(u) \cdot F_f(v) \quad (2)$$

Where μ is the Möbius function ($\mu(1)=1$, $\mu(n)=0$ if n is divisible by the square of a prime number , $\mu(n)=(-1)^k$ if n is the product of k different prime numbers)

If f is the Smarandache function and $n = p^\alpha$ then :

$$F_s(p^\alpha) = \sum_{j=1}^{\alpha} s(p^j)$$

In [2] it is proved that

$$s(p^j) = p - 1 \cdot j + \alpha_{(p)}(j) \quad (3)$$

Where $\alpha_{(p)}(j)$ is the sum of the digits of the integer j , written in the generalised scale

$$[p] = a_1(p) , a_2(p) , \dots , a_k(p) , \dots$$

with $a_i(p) = (p^i - 1)/(p - 1)$

So

$$F_s(p^\alpha) = \sum_{j=1}^{\alpha} s(p^j) = (p - 1) \frac{\alpha(\alpha + 1)}{2} + \sum_{j=1}^{\alpha} \alpha_{(p)}(j) \quad (4)$$

Using the expresion of α given by (3) it results

$$(\alpha + 1)(s(p^\alpha) - \alpha_{(p)}(\alpha)) = 2(F_s(p^\alpha) - \sum_{j=1}^{\alpha} \alpha_{(p)}(j))$$

In the following we give an algorithm to calculate the sum in the right hand of (4). For this, let $\alpha_{(p)} = \overline{k_s \cdot k_{s-1} \cdot \dots \cdot k_1}$ the expression of α in the scale $[p]$ and $j_{(p)} = \overline{k_s \cdot k_{s-1} \cdot \dots \cdot k_1}$. We shall say that k_j are the digits of order i , for $j = 1, 2, \dots, \alpha$. To calculate the sum of all the digits of order i , let $\nu_i = \alpha - a_i(p) + 1$. Now we consider two cases :

(i) if $k_i \neq 0$, let :

$z_i(\alpha) = (\overline{k_s k_{s-1} \dots k_{i+1}})_{u=\alpha(p)}$, the equality $u = a_i(p)$ denoting that for the number written between parantheses, the classe of units is $a_i(p)$.

Then $z_i(\alpha)$ is the number of all zeros of order i for the integers $j \leq \alpha$ and $\alpha'_i = \nu_i(\alpha) - z_i(\alpha)$ is the number of the non-null digits.

(ii) if $k_i = 0$, let β the greatest number, less than α , having a non-null digit of order i . Then β is of the form :

$\beta_{(p)} = \overline{k_s k_{s-1} \dots k_{i+2} (k_{i+1} - 1) p 0 0 \dots 0}$ and of course $s_i(\alpha) = s_i(\beta)$. It results that there exist $\alpha'_i(\beta)$ non-null digits of order i .

Let A_i, B_i, r_i, ρ_i given by equalities :

$$\alpha'_i = A_i((p-1)a_i(p) + 1) + r_i = A_i(a_{i+1}(p) - a_i(p)) + r_i$$

$$r_i = B_i a_i(p) + \rho_i$$

Then

$$s_i(\alpha) = A_i a_i(p) \frac{p(p-1)}{2} + A_i p + a_i(p) \frac{B_i(B_i+1)}{2} + \rho_i(B_i+1)$$

and

$$\sum_{j=1}^{\alpha} \sigma_{(p)}(j) = \sum_{i=1}^{\alpha} s_i(\alpha) = \frac{p(p-1)}{2} \sum_{i \geq 1} A_i a_i(p) + p \sum_{i \geq 1} A_i +$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \geq 1} a_i(p) B_i (B_i + 1) + \sum_{i \geq 1} \rho_i (B_i + 1)$$

For example if $\alpha = 149$ and $p = 3$ it results :

$$[3] \quad 1, 4, 13, 40, 121, \dots$$

$$\alpha_{(3)} = 10202, \nu_1(\alpha) = (1020)_{u=\alpha_1(3)} = 48, \alpha_1 = \nu_1(\alpha) - z_1(\alpha) = 101$$

$$\text{For } \beta_{(3)} = 10130 = 146 \text{ it results } \nu_2(\beta) = 143, z_2(\beta) =$$

$$(101)_{u=\alpha_2(3)} = u_3 + u = 3u_2 + 1 + u = 3(3u + 1) + 1 + u = 44,$$

$$\alpha_2 = 99, \nu_3(\alpha) = 137, z_3(\alpha) = (10)_{u=\alpha_3(3)} = 40, \alpha_3 = 97.$$

$$\text{For } \beta_{(3)} = 3000 = 120 \text{ it results } \nu_4(\beta) = 81, z_4(\beta) = 0, \alpha_4 = 108.$$

$$\nu_5(\alpha) = 29, z_5(\alpha) = 0, \alpha_5 = 29, \text{ and}$$

$$A_1 = \left[\frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_2 - \alpha_1} \right] = 33, r_1 = 2, B_1 = \left[\frac{z}{\alpha_1} \right], \rho_1 = 0, s_1 = 201$$

Analogously $s_2 = 165, s_3 = 145, s_4 = 123$ and $s_5 = 129$, so

$$\sum_{i=1}^{140} \alpha_{(3)}(i) = 633, F_s(3^{140}) = 22983.$$

Now let us consider $n = p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot \dots \cdot p_k$, with $p_1 < p_2 < \dots < p_k$ prime numbers. Of course, $S(n) = p_k$ and from

$$F_s(1) = S(1) = 0$$

$$F_s(p_1) = S(1) + S(p_1) = p_1$$

$$F_s(p_1 \cdot p_2) = p_1 + 2p_2 = F(p_1) + 2p_2$$

$$F_s(p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot p_3) = p_1 + 2p_2 + 2^2 p_3 = F(p_1 \cdot p_2) + 2^2 p_3$$

it results :

$$F_s(p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot \dots \cdot p_k) = F(p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot \dots \cdot p_{k-1}) + 2^{k-1} p^k$$

That is :

$$F_s(p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot \dots \cdot p_k) = \sum_{i=1}^k 2^{i-1} p_i$$

The equality (2) becomes :

$$\begin{aligned} p_k = S(n) &= \sum_{u \cdot v = n} \mu(n) F_s(v) = \\ &= F(n) - \sum_i F\left(\frac{n}{p_i}\right) + \sum_{i,j} F\left(\frac{n}{p_i p_j}\right) + \dots + \sum_{i=1}^k F(p_i) \end{aligned}$$

and because $F(p_i) = p_i$, it results :

$$F\left(\frac{n}{p_i}\right) = F(p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot \dots \cdot p_{i-1} \cdot p_{i+1} \cdot \dots \cdot p_k) = \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} 2^{j-1} p_j + \sum_{j=i+1}^k 2^{j-1} p_j =$$

$$= F(p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot \dots \cdot p_{i-1}) + 2^{i-1} F(p_{i+1} \cdot p_{i+2} \cdot \dots \cdot p_k).$$

Analogously,

$$F\left(\frac{n}{p_i p_j}\right) = F(p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot \dots \cdot p_{i-1}) + 2^{i-1} F(p_{i+1} \cdot p_{i+2} \cdot \dots \cdot p_{j-1}) +$$

$$+ 2^{j-1} F(p_{j+1} \cdot \dots \cdot p_k)$$

Finally, we point out as an open problem that, by the Shapiro's theorem, if it exist a numerical function $g : \mathbb{N} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$g(n) = \sum_{d|n} P(d) S\left(\frac{n}{d}\right)$$

were P is a totally multiplicative function and $P(1) = 1$, then

$$S(n) = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) P(d) g\left(\frac{n}{d}\right)$$

REFERENCES

1. M. Andrei, C. Dumitrescu, V. Seleacu, L. Tutescu, St. Zanfir, *Some Remarks on the Smarandache Function* (Smarandache Function Journal, Vol.4, No.1 (1994) to appear).
2. M. Andrei, C. Dumitrescu, V. Seleacu, L. Tutescu, St. Zanfir *La fonction de Smarandache. une nouvelle fonction dans la theorie des nombres* (Congres International Henri Poincaré, Nancy 14-18 May 1994).
3. W. Sierpinski *Elementary Theory of Numbers* (Panstwowe, Wydawnictwo Naukowe, Warszawa, 1964).

4. F.Smarandache *A Function in the Number theory* (An. Univ. Timisoara Ser. St. Mat. V **XXVIII**, fasc. 1, (1980), 79-88).

Current address : University of Craiova, Department of Mathematics, Str. A.I.Cuza, Nr.13, Craiova (1100), Romania.